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Recent Political Movements in a Changing World

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Abstract

Recent discussions in the theory of international relations show that international politics as an autonomous field of reality takes place around the possibility of a moral, social and political conceptualization. According to the critical theory of international politics developed by Andrew Linklater, it is seen that the modern idea of the international as a historical-social reality has developed. In the normative sense, it is argued that the relationship between humanity and citizenship is based on the definition of a particularist political ontology. Starting from an ethical universalist perspective, he proposes a more universalist, less unequal and more sensitive to difference global political theory with the transformation of the socio-political community on normative, historical-sociological and practical levels, as well as providing a comprehensive analysis of its social and political conditions with the principles of difference, plurality and diversity in global politics. We must reconcile. In other words, like chess, the course of the game is changed by mutual strategies. It is a fact that the most basic rule of the game is to keep the king as far away from danger as possible and not bring the battle closer to the king. During the Cold War, the ground that we can call the chessboard was the world geography. With the disintegration of the USSR in 1991, the Cold War literature was thought to be over, and a lot of work was conducted on it. One of the most notable events of recent times has been the occupation of Ukraine by different nations, empires and states throughout history due to its strategic location. Located at an important crossroads, Ukraine is a region where both east-west and north-south corridors intersect. The Black Sea is found at an important crossroads between Europe, Asia and the Middle East. Being next to the Black Sea, the southwest corner of the sea is connected to the Atlantic Ocean

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via the Bosphorus, the Marmara Sea and the Aegean Sea, and the Mediterranean Sea. Likewise, it has an eastern connection with the Sea of Azov via the Kerch Strait (Majdi , 2021). In short, the security of the geographical regions listed above is important for the dominance and control of the Black Sea. After independence, Ukraine experienced tough times economically , political problems were added with the Orange Revolution in 2004, in addition to the economic demanding situation (Ozturk, 2014). The political problems experienced, and the effect of the Orange Revolution brought the Cold War, which appeared after the Second World War and turned the world into two poles, on the agenda again. The developments have brought the EU, NATO and Russia face to face over the years.

Keywords: *Political Movements, Recent Politics, Politics of Countries, Political Mobility, Ukraine International Political Mobility*

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Introduction

Yanukovich won the 2010 election; the election declared the Orange Revolution to be over. The first breakthrough that Yanukovich made after he came to power can show that the Russian Black Sea Fleet in the Crimean Peninsula extended the agreement period, which will expire in 2017, until 2042. Empowering Russia and Putin have brought their desire to set up dominance in the former USSR lands along with these developments. It is not a coincidence that Russia, one of the strongest countries in the world in terms of army, played its first move on chess through economy and strengthened its ground with the existing underground resources. The location of Ukraine is especially important for Russia.

The other actors of the game are the EU and NATO. The European Union acts to keep stability and peace in the region. The organization, which was found on an economic basis, began to become an important power with the expansions it made after the changes that took place in the world in the early 1990s (Hairless, 2014). After the Cold War, the EU, NATO and Russia continued to expand from west to east and from east to west towards the Black Sea. This enlargement is especially the expansion of the EU and NATO over the former Warsaw Pact members and USSR states. This point was perceived as a security threat for Russia, and according to some thinkers, it caused the Ukraine Crisis to erupt.

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Ukraine Crisis

Ukraine, according to its constitution, is a unitary state in the country. Ukraine administratively consists of 24 provinces. In this structure, Crimea was accepted until 2014. It is important that the capital cities of Kyiv and Sevastopol are referred to as cities with special status. The ethnic structure of the country consists of Ukrainians and Russians.

The collapse of the USSR after the Cold War caused it to lose its dominance in the regions where it was active. Based on the knowledge that conventional weapons will cause destruction, great states avoid such hot conflicts.

Russia's policies in terms of the Ukraine crisis; Wearing down the pro-Western government in Ukraine and bringing a pro-Russian government to power in the long run is a separate issue that needs to be evaluated. Preventing Ukraine's rapprochement with the West seems to be a separate strategy. Supplying the support of the citizens in the country and the people in the Russian-speaking country is also included in certain policies (Karabulut, 2016). The implementation of a deterrent force, together with the military units sent to the borders against the measures taken by Ukraine, includes the aid of ammunition to the insurgent under humanitarian aid (Mastriano, 2014).

Based on this information, it is seen that the Russian media has successfully implemented the information war mentioned by Mastriano. Russian sources emphasized that the crisis in

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Ukraine was purely civil conflict/civil war. We see that ammunition shipments are made by legal entities and private groups. How valid it is to defend the arguments that there are no Russian soldiers in the conflicts in the region, and those who are affiliated with the Russian Army are members of the former army is another matter of debate. It has avoided the active involvement of the EU and NATO in the crisis.

Pro-Russian Yanukovych

The pro-Russian Yanukovych came to power in 2010, supported by The Orange Revolution by the West ended. Violence has started to increase in the country. Towards the end of 2013, reminiscent of the Orange Revolution, the desire of the masses to force the Eurasian Union pro-Eurasian Union President Yanukovych , who found them with authoritarianism and corruption, continued their cooperation with the EU itself. These issues brought only the overthrow of Yanukovych , but also a series of critical developments with the domino effect (Sun, 2014). Thus, the Euro Square events have appeared.

East Ukraine Crisis

In the above section, a partial basis of the process up to the current crisis is explained. The pro-Western Orange Revolution began with the change of administration in 2004. From this point of view, the main axis of the article is to think and fill this ongoing gap in technology related technology from international relations from the perspective of the Science-Technology-Society . The revolution in information technology forces countries to set up closer relations with each other and to catch up with the developments in the world .

Within the framework of the analysis, the security feelings of the European Union were revealed. It has tried to illuminate the European security situation and the possible role that **THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER WHERE TOGETHER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE : +49(177) 8684-353 EMAIL: ASI@EUROPE.DE**

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could or could be expected for Turkey in European security. In the document, the general framework of the European security strategy was decided, the security problems, the search for solutions and the measures were taken to be explained. To better understand the content of the mentioned document, it is necessary to focus on the nature of the European Union.

This attempt has also failed, as nation-states have made reservations about delegating their sovereign powers in overly sensitive areas such as security and defence, to the common European authorities. Devignon Reports of the 1970s with more modest and small steps

A new proposal was called the "European Political Cooperation" (ASI) was set up (Ulger, 2002:64).

example in this respect , the economic crisis management, " Rapid reaction It would be correct to remember that aid was given to Afghanistan within the framework of mechanism " (Preventing Conflicts Assistance Mechanism). Also, Afghanistan has contributed to border control and reorganization of the police force. Therefore, the EU, on the one hand, limited its movements within the framework of the UN provisions, and on the other hand, did not make war . and to improve its troop deployment capability, essentially a similar approach to US political culture, but to the US way of life includes some negativity that is quite common in Europe.

Conclusion

It will be in the interest of the EU that the neighboring countries also get a certain share of it. Thus, the EU will not only be able to get rid of the appearance of a bloc but will also contribute to the formation of a zone of peace, which is formed / will be formed by states governed by democracies. The point is that the document emphasizes as the third strategic goal is the proposition that the international order should be shaped based on multilateral relations and

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law. Transatlantic relations were counted as the basis of the current international system, and it was emphasized that these relations were shaped according to international legal norms. Therefore, it has been underlined that international and regional organizations are important for a prosperous and peaceful world order. In this regard, the EU security strategy has clearly differed from the US national security strategy. Particular attention was paid to the successful crisis management of the EU in the Balkans and an example of what the EU could achieve was shown. It was emphasized that similar successes could be achieved in other regions if the member states adopt a common stance .

It emphasized that foreign relations should be blended and directed to the same political goal and agenda. In this context, it was said that foreign trade, development aid, foreign and security policies should be coordinated. On the other hand, Russia was not given an EU membership perspective and a separate Russia Strategy was accepted (EU-RUSSIA SUMMIT 2005; MOMMSEN, 2004: 483-502), while it was accepted that Turkey could become a full member of the EU. Despite this, the fact that Turkey is not referred to the document assumes that either avoids strengthening Ankara's hand in the accession negotiations or to prioritize Russia and that Turkey's possible contribution to EU security will be weak. This is a critical issue that needs to be discussed in our opinion. In fact, the Balkans, Mediterranean Periphery, Middle East and Caucasus regions are listed as sensitive areas for European security in the document. There is no doubt that the specified regions are also important for Turkish security. Turkey is in a country at the crossroads of the specified regions and has the potential to affect the security of the region as well as being affected by European developments.

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